

Highly active and recyclable ZSM-5 anchored rhodium(I) complexes of S-triazene derivatives for the catalytic hydrogenation of organic substrates

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Abstract : The HZSM-5 was used to immobilize the homogeneous Rh^I complexes of S-triazene derivatives. They were found very efficient towards the catalytic hydrogenation of alkenes, alkynes, nitrocompounds, benzaldehyde and benzil at 25 °C and 2.07×10^3 KNm⁻² pressure of molecular hydrogen as compare to its homogeneous counterpart. At this temperature and pressure of molecular hydrogen, ZSM-5 anchored Rh^I complexes could be used repeatedly. DMF-toluene (1 : 2) mixed solvents medium was found suitable for these complexes. No diminished catalytic activity was observed even after 10–15 repeated catalytic runs. This indicated that negligible leaching out phenomenon of the metal or metal complexes.

Keywords : Rh^I complexes, nitrocompounds, alkene, alkyne, catalytic hydrogenation.

Introduction

The transition metal complexes have long been used as catalysts for the dihydrogen reduction of organic substrates such as nitrocompounds¹⁻¹³, alkenes¹⁴⁻²¹, alkynes²¹⁻²⁶, aldehydes²⁷⁻³⁰, ketones²⁹⁻³², Schiff bases³³ and nitriles³⁴. A good number of Rh^I non-orthometallated and orthometallated complexes have also been found to exhibit very good catalytic activity towards dihydrogen reduction of wide variety of unsaturated organic compounds³⁵⁻³⁸. Catalyst decomposition and poor reproducibility at the time of its repeated use was major disadvantage associated with these catalytic systems. Among the numerous homogeneous Rh^I catalyst used for the dihydrogen reduction of various unsaturated organic substrates^{1-3,15,22,33,34,39-42} only few are found stable enough to reduce nitrocompounds, ketones and nitriles⁴³⁻⁴⁶ and in most of the cases the reduction mechanism could not be well established^{47,48}. In our previous communication we have studied the catalytic activity of Pd^{II} and Rh^I complexes towards various unsaturated organic substrates in homogeneous phase^{49,50}.

The heterogenised-homogeneous catalysts exhibit ex-

cellent catalytic activity for the hydrogenation of various organic substrates, over its homogeneous counterpart⁵¹⁻⁵⁷. This paper introduces the excellent catalytic activity of ZSM-5 anchored Rh^I-S-triazene complexes for the hydrogenation of wide variety of organic substrates. Immobilized Rh^I complexes was found more stable, thermopotent, eco-friendly and industrially applicable as compare to its homogeneous counterpart.

Results and discussion

ZSM-5 was used to immobilize the homogeneous Rh^I-S-triazene complexes (ZSM-5 is an aluminum silicate with high silica content). It consists of two intersecting channel systems defined by ten membered ring of tetrahedral. The channels are ellipsoidal with ten ring openings having approximate free dimensions $5.4 \times 5.5 \times 10^{-8}$ cm (straight channel) and $5.1 \times 5.4 \times 10^{-8}$ cm (sinusoidal channel) (A gram of so of this type of catalyst support has an internal surface area equal to that of a standard tennis court).

The ZSM-5 anchored Rh^I complexes were found to be highly active towards reduction of alkenes, alkynes, nitroaromatics and benzyl under high pressure conditions.

ZSM-5 anchored complexes were able to increase the rate of hydrogenation, turn over number and yield of products drastically. In case of homogeneous Rh^I-S-triazene complexes, the maximum initial turn over number is only 27 min⁻¹ 50 but in ZSM-5 anchored Rh^I-S-triazene complexes the turn over number increases to 45 min⁻¹. A comparative graph of the efficiency of ZSM-5 anchored complexes over the homogeneous ones is shown in Fig. 1. The optimum conditions, nature and % of yield of various products with recycling activity of the ZSM-5 anchored [Rh(OEt-T)(CO)₂], Rh(DEt-AT)(CO)₂, [Rh(DEt-ATH₂)(CO)₂] have given in Tables 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Fig. 1. Comparative chart of turnover no. of hydrogenation of organic substrates using homogeneous Rh-S-triazene complex and ZSM-5 anchored Rh-S-triazene complex.

The nature of products obtained for a particular substrate using different complexes as catalyst were almost same but the rate of hydrogenation, turn over number and yield of different products was found to depend on the nature of the catalyst. [Rh(OEt-T)(CO)₂] was found highly but not equally active as compared to other Rh^I complexes. The ZSM-5 anchored Rh^I complexes may be placed in the following order according to their catalytic activities :

The greater activity of ZSM-5 anchored Rh^I complexes over its homogeneous counterpart may be due to the higher amount of more electronegative silicon and lower alumina content which make the ZSM-5 stronger acid and so the complexes are more catalytically active. In homogeneous phase the Rh^I complexes were found susceptible to aerobic oxidation leading to Rh^{III} species but ZSM-5 anchored Rh^I complexes has more environmental tolerance. DMF-toluene (1 : 2) mixed solvents medium was found suitable for these complexes.

The final products in case of alkenes reduction were mainly the corresponding alkanes. The extent of isomerization was far less as compared to the homogeneous

Table 1. Optimum conditions, nature and % yield of products with recycling activity of ZSM-5 anchored [Rh(OEt-T)(CO)₂]

Substrate	Rh content (before use) g. atom/lit × 10 ⁻³	Products	1st Cycle		3rd Cycle		5th Cycle		Rh content (after use) g. atom/lit × 10 ⁻³
			Initial turn over no.	Yield (%)	Initial turn over no.	Yield (%)	Initial turn over no.	Yield (%)	
Styrene ^a	2.63	Ethylbenzene	40	98	39	98	38	98	2.63
1-Hexene ^a	2.63	1-Hexane	25	97	24	97	23	97	2.63
Cyclohexene ^a	2.63	Cyclohexane	15	96	14	96	13	96	2.63
Fumaric acid ^a	2.63	Succinic acid	12	94	11	94	10	94	2.63
Phenylacetylene ^a	2.63	Ethylbenzene	22	97	21	97	20	97	2.63
Nitrobenzene ^b	2.63	Aniline	18	98	17	98	16	98	2.63
<i>p</i> -Chloro-nitrobenzene ^b	2.63	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	15	97	14	97	13	97	2.63
<i>p</i> -Dinitrobenzene ^b	2.63	<i>p</i> -Phenylene-diamine	12	96	11	96	10	96	2.63
1-Nitro-naphthalene ^b	2.63	1-Amino-naphthalene	10	95	9	95	8	95	2.63
Benzaldehyde ^c	2.63	Benzylalcohol	12	96	11	96	10	96	2.63

[Subs] = 0.50 mol/lit, medium = DMF-toluene, total vol. = 15 ml, pressure of H₂ = 2.07 × 10³ KNm⁻² [(a) at 25 °C, (b) at 60 °C, (c) at 50 °C].

Table 2. Optimum conditions, nature and % yield of products with recycling activity of ZSM-5 anchored [Rh(DEt-AT)(CO)₂]

Substrate	Rh content (before use) g.atom/lit × 10 ⁻³	Products	1st Cycle		3rd Cycle		5th Cycle		Rh content (after use) g.atom/lit × 10 ⁻³
			Initial turn	Yield	Initial turn	Yield	Initial turn	Yield	
			over no.	(%)	over no.	(%)	over no.	(%)	
Styrene ^a	2.63	Ethylbenzene	39	98	38	98	37	98	2.63
1-Hexene ^a	2.63	1-Hexane	23	96	22	96	21	96	2.63
Cyclohexene ^a	2.63	Cyclohexane	13	95	12	95	11	95	2.63
Fumaric acid ^a	2.63	Succinic acid	11	93	10	93	9	93	2.63
Phenylacetylene ^a	2.63	Ethylbenzene	21	96	20	96	19	96	2.63
Nitrobenzene ^b	2.63	Aniline	17	98	16	98	15	98	2.63
<i>p</i> -Chloro-nitrobenzene ^b	2.63	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	14	96	13	96	12	96	2.63
<i>p</i> -Dinitrobenzene ^b	2.63	<i>p</i> -Phenylene-diamine	11	96	10	96	9	96	2.63
1-Nitro-naphthalene ^b	2.63	1-Amino-naphthalene	9	94	8	94	7	94	2.63
Benzaldehyde ^c	2.63	Benzylalcohol	11	96	10	96	9	96	2.63

[Subs] = 0.50 mol/lit, medium = DMF-toluene, total vol. = 15 ml, pressure of H₂ = 2.07 × 10³ KNm⁻² [(a) at 25 °C, (b) at 60 °C, (c) at 50 °C].

Table 3. Optimum conditions, nature and % yield of products with recycling activity of ZSM-5 anchored [Rh(DEt-ATH₂)(CO)₂]

Substrate	Rh content (before use) g.atom/lit × 10 ⁻³	Products	1st Cycle		3rd Cycle		5th Cycle		Rh content (after use) g.atom/lit × 10 ⁻³
			Initial turn	Yield	Initial turn	Yield	Initial turn	Yield	
			over no.	(%)	over no.	(%)	over no.	(%)	
Styrene ^a	2.63	Ethylbenzene	37	98	36	98	35	98	2.63
1-Hexene ^a	2.63	1-Hexane	22	96	21	96	20	96	2.63
Cyclohexene ^a	2.63	Cyclohexane	12	95	11	95	10	95	2.63
Fumaric acid ^a	2.63	Succinic acid	9	93	8	93	7	93	2.63
Phenyl acetylene ^a	2.63	Ethylbenzene	19	96	18	96	17	96	2.63
Nitrobenzene ^b	2.63	Aniline	15	98	14	98	13	98	2.63
<i>p</i> -Chloro-nitrobenzene ^b	2.63	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	12	96	11	96	10	96	2.63
<i>p</i> -Dinitrobenzene ^b	2.63	<i>p</i> -Phenylene-diamine	9	96	8	96	7	96	2.63
1-Nitro-naphthalene ^b	2.63	1-Amino-naphthalene	8	94	7	94	6	94	2.63
Benzaldehyde ^c	2.63	Benzylalcohol	10	96	9	96	8	96	2.63

[Subs] = 0.50 mol/lit, medium = DMF-toluene, total vol. = 15 ml, pressure of H₂ = 2.07 × 10³ KNm⁻² [(a) at 25 °C, (b) at 60 °C, (c) at 50 °C].

catalyst. This was probably due to the very good reactant shape selectivity, transition state shape selectivity and product shape selectivity of ZSM-5. It requires a particular type of orientation of the coordinated alkene so that linear alkyl complex formation was preferred. Figs. 2 and 3 clearly shows the catalytic hydrogenation of hex-1-ene by using homogeneous [Rh(OEt-T)(CO)₂] and ZSM-

5 anchored [Rh(OEt-T)(CO)₂] complexes respectively.

The reduction of nitroaromatics was found to be depending substantially on the reaction temperature provided other conditions remained same. The rate of reduction at room temperature was very slow and increased with temperature upto 60 °C and then decreased sharply with increasing temperature. This fall in rate might be

Table 4. Analytical data of the complexes

Complexes	Colour	Yield (in g and %)	M.p. (°C)	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd)			
					M	N	C	H
[Rh(OR-T)(CO) ₂] (1)	Yellow	0.34 70	170	390.0 (390.16)	26.32 (26.38)	14.40 (14.36)	40.08 (40.02)	2.80 (2.84)
[Rh(DEt-ATH ₂)(CO) ₂] (2)	Yellow	0.35 68	175	419.10 (419.25)	24.50 (24.54)	16.55 (18.70)	42.95 (42.97)	4.30 (4.33)
[Rh(DEt-AT)(CO) ₂] (3)	Yellow	0.34 65	80	417.12 (417.23)	24.50 (24.66)	16.75 (16.78)	43.00 (43.18)	3.85 (3.86)

Parenthesis indicated the calculated value.

Fig. 2. Catalytic hydrogenation of hex-1-ene with [Rh(OEt-T)(CO)₂].

Fig. 3. Catalytic hydrogenation of hex-1-ene with ZSM-5 anchored [Rh(OEt-T)(CO)₂].

due to formation of some stable species inside the cavities of ZSM-5 at comparatively higher temperature. The products obtained from these nitrocompounds were always the corresponding amines and to partially reduced compounds were possible to isolate anywhere. The partially

reduced nitrocompounds such as phenylhydroxyamines, nitrosobenzene, etc. could be reduced completely to the corresponding amines but azo and azoxy compounds could not be reduced to the corresponding amines. Hence it may be concluded that nitroaromatics were reduced without the formation of any coupled product.

Experimental

Materials and equipments :

Analytical grade chemicals, dry and ultra pure quality of N₂, Ar and H₂ were always used. AR grade solvents and liquid substrates were purified by distillation and dried on molecular sieves (4 Å). S-Triazines[†] OR-TH, DEt-ATH₃, DEt-ATH were prepared and purified using literature methods⁵⁸. RhCl₃.3H₂O of Arora-Matthey Ltd. was used without further purification. Catalytic hydrogenation were carried out by using J. T. Baker (USA) analyzed DMF. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen of the complexes were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN Elemental analyser. Rhodium was not estimated rather it was calculated by difference. Molecular weight of the complexes was determined by using KNAUER, DAMPE-FDRUCK-Osmometer. UV/Vis and IR spectra were recorded on Pyeunicam PU8600 and Pyeunicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer respectively. The product mixture were analyzed by TLC on silica gel coated plastic sheets (Merck Silica gel F₂₅₄) and by GLC (5700 Nucon gas chromatograph) using Apiezon.L, Carbowax 20 M, SE-30 columns. Rh^I-S-triazene complexes were prepared, purified and characterized by using literature methods⁵⁰. Colour, yield, mol. wt., m.p. and other analytical data are given in Tables 3, 4, 5.

[†]OR-TH : 2-*o*-Hydroxyphenyl-4-amino-6-alkoxy-1,3,5-triazene. DEt-ATH₃ : 2-*o*-Hydroxyphenyl-4-amino-6-diethylamino-1,2-dihydro-1,3,5-triazene. DEt-ATH : 2-*o*-Hydroxyphenyl-4-amino-6-diethylamino-1,3,5-triazene.

Table 5. Electronic spectral data of the ligands and complexes

Comps.	dd/CT transition (cm ⁻¹)	n-π, π-π* (cm ⁻¹)
OR-TH	—	29840, 36360, 40750, 41650
DEt-ATH ₃	—	29850, 36360, 40750, 46580
DEt-ATH	—	29850, 36370, 40855, 41640
[Rh(OR-T)(CO) ₂]	22472	36360, 40323, 41650
[Rh(DEt-ATH ₂)(CO) ₂]	21978	36350, 40716, 46580
[Rh(DEt-AT)(CO) ₂]	22358	36360, 40816, 41640

Table 6. IR spectral data of the complexes (cm⁻¹)

Comps.	νNH/NH ₂	νOH phenol	νC=O	νNH ₂	νCO phenol
OR-TH	3460–3230	2870	—	1615	1525
DEt-ATH ₃	3460–3230	2875	—	1615	1520
DEt-ATH	3395–3240	2865	—	1615	1525
[Rh(OR-T)(CO) ₂]	3390–3300	—	2080–2000	1615	1545
[Rh(DEt-ATH ₂)(CO) ₂]	3455–3220	—	2085–2000	1615	1535
[Rh(DEt-AT)(CO) ₂]	3395–3230	—	2080–2019	1615	1545

Preparation of complexes :

Preparation of dicarbonyl(*S*-triazino)rhodium(I) (*Rh*(OR-*T*)(CO)₂] (**1**) :

RhCl₃.3H₂O (0.26 g; 1.242 mmol) in deoxygenated DMF (10 ml) was stirred with *S*-triazine (0.313 g; 1.355 mmol) in dinitrogen atmosphere for half an hour. The solution was then refluxed under dinitrogen atmosphere for 2 h in oil bath. During the first 10 min the solution changed its colour from dark red to yellow. The solution was cooled to room temperature and diluted with deoxygenated water (35 ml). A yellow precipitate appeared. The reaction mixture was kept at 5 °C for 1 h and then filtered under dinitrogen atmosphere. The precipitate was washed with deoxygenated water and acetone successively and dried in vacuum. The other two rhodium(*S*-triazine) complexes i.e. [Rh(DEt-ATH₂)(CO)₂] (**2**), [Rh(DEt-AT)(CO)₂] (**3**) were prepared following the above procedure.

Immobilization of homogeneous Rh^I complexes with ZSM-5 :

Immobilizations of homogeneous Rh^I complexes were carried out by using literature methods^{59–63}. Commercially available ZSM-5 was used as a solid support for the homogeneous Rh^I complexes. The HZSM-5 was washed thoroughly with methanol and then dried in oven first at 60 °C for 2 h and then at 300 °C in muffle-furnaces for 6 h. Pre-heated and pre-activated HZSM-5

was then dipped into the respective solution of soluble Rh^I complexes. Solution was stirred mechanically with the help of shaker in argon atmosphere for 48 h. When almost all the Rh^I complexes was absorbed/adsorbed by ZSM-5 as marked by the appearance of a colourless clear solution. The impregnated ZSM-5 was filtered and washed thoroughly with appropriate solvent to remove the surface adhered solution of the complexes. Impregnated ZSM-5 was dried under vacuum and finally calculated below the decomposition temperature of the respective complexes for 8–48 h. Extent of impregnation (% in w/w) was determined both by weighing the residue left after vacuum evaporation of filtrate and by estimating rhodium and nitrogen in the impregnated ZSM-5. Extent of impregnation was varied from 0.005–0.012% (w/w) with respect to ZSM-5 and measured by using Electronic Balance of DENVER INSTRUMENT (max. 210 g; *d* = 0.1 mg).

Experimental procedure for high pressure hydrogenation :

High pressure hydrogenation was carried out in high pressure autoclave. The substrate solution in DMF-toluene mixed solvent system containing immobilized complex was taking in the autoclave and the reaction was conducted at a constant temperature in the range 25–60 °C by immersing the autoclave in a constant temperature oil-bath. The autoclave was first evacuated and then purged several times with hydrogen. The hydrogen gas was in-

produced till the desired pressure ($2.76 \times 10^3 \text{ KNm}^{-2}$) was attained. Stirring of the reaction mixture was started only when it attained a constant desired temperature and pressure. At regular time interval, the product mixture was taken out by hot release. By using these immobilized Rh^{I} complexes the reductions of alkenes were performed at 25°C while those of nitroaromatics were studied at different temperature ranging from $25\text{--}60^\circ\text{C}$ to obtain substantial rate of hydrogen.

Separation, identification and estimation of the hydrogenated products :

At the end of the catalytic run, the colour of impregnated ZSM-5 was found to change depending upon the nature of substrates used and the reaction conditions. After the catalytic run the impregnated ZSM-5 was filtered off, washed thoroughly and dried while the filtrate was used for the separation of the different components. The components were separated and identified by following the same general procedure. Finally they were estimated by GLC using SE-30, Carbowax-20M and Sebaconitrile-25% column. The choice of column was made according to the nature of the components to be estimated.

Recycle of the catalyst :

It was always found possible to recycle the ZSM-5 anchored Rh^{I} complexes from the reaction mixture at the end of each catalytic run. At the end of catalytic run impregnated ZSM-5 was usually washed well with dry DMF and CCl_4 successfully. It could be used several times (10–15 times) without any diminished catalytic activity.

Conclusion :

ZSM-5 anchored Rh^{I} complexes of S-triazene derivatives were used as efficient and recyclable catalyst for hydrogenation of a number of organic substrates. These immobilized complexes are more efficient as compared to its homogeneous counterpart. In case of alkenes, the yield of hydrogenated products was increased by decreasing isomerization due to shape selectivity of immobilized catalyst. DMF-toluene (1 : 2) mixed solvent system was found best solvent for these catalytic systems. The complexes could be repeatedly used several times (10–15 times) without any diminished catalytic activity.

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